

**ROLE OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN UPBRINGING
CHILD IN FAMILY AND MAKHALLA**

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The purpose of this article is to study the importance of the development of the spiritual and moral environment in the family and the community, as well as the areas in which the family and the community today have an impact on the moral and educational development and preservation of the national spirit. study, analysis of external factors in the process of studying or living abroad, the effects of external globalization, their significance along with the scope of influence, proposals and solutions that develop not only education but also the moral environment in accordance with our national mentality and national spirit identification, the close connection between the spiritual, moral and spiritual upbringing environment, the importance of the place of life, the teaching of foreign languages to the child while preserving the national spirit in the age of modern globalization and information flows, the sanctity of the family and the community to convey to the younger generation in a new way

Keywords: Neighborhood, universal values, national spirit, spiritual and moral environment, globalization, information age, acceleration process, mentality, national idea, psychological immunity

Quote: "Today, the neighborhood should be a reflection of the principles of justice in our society," he said. It should be a place where people come and

express their opinions, suggestions, concerns and find solutions to their problems. "(Shavkat Mirziyoyev - President of the Republic of Uzbekistan).

Quote: "People who know the language know, living in harmony with modernity requires a young generation that knows modern languages" (Shavkat Mirziyoyev - President of the Republic of Uzbekistan).

From ancient times, our people have revered the mahalla as a place of national values and good deeds. Good qualities such as bringing up children, kindness, harmony, taking care of the needs, people in need of help, holding weddings, hashar and celebrations in public, being together on good and bad positions formed in the same neighborhood.

From time immemorial, in Uzbek mahallas, such qualities as humanity, kindness and generosity have been an integral part of the national mentality of the people. In Uzbeks, a child grows up first in the family and then in the neighborhood. This, in turn, embodies in the minds of people such qualities as cohesiveness, mutual support, respect for others, respect for the elder, and respect for the younger. The role of local self-government bodies and mahallas in the system of civil society institutions is priceless. Because, unlike other countries, the institution of the neighborhood is developing in our country as a socio-spiritual phenomenon that has been tested and deeply rooted for thousands of years, uniting the people. Especially in the current transition to a market economy, it is manifested in the preservation of the traditions and values of our people, the unification of our youth, the strengthening of feelings of kindness among them. Today's rapid changes, like all other spheres, require an analysis of the neighborhood and its management system, socio-political, economic and spiritual activities on the basis of new criteria. One of the important tasks is to form a new structure of the self-governing body that can meet the requirements of the times, to effectively organize its system.

It is no coincidence that the first priority of the "Action Strategy" for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 is "Increasing the role and effectiveness of the Mahalla Institute in public administration." Today it is expedient to put forward the following proposals for more effective organization and development of community activities in raising the morale of young people. A number of practical reforms are being carried out today to deep the role of mahallas in the society, which is an institution of citizen self-government that is not found in other countries of the world, and to ensure the continuity of reforms in this area.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "If we want to understand the spiritual position and the situation in every home, in the whole country, we will be able to see a vivid picture of the real picture, first of all, in the life of the neighborhood." of course. After all, if the family is an eye-opener for us, the neighborhood is a small homeland within our sacred Motherland. The mahalla is made up of families. Just as the family is the main link in society, our mahallas are the link between our nation and our national spirit. Just as children grow up in a family, so does a family grow up in a community. As a result, the neighborhood, as the closest adviser to the family, is at the fore front of issues related to the spiritual and moral education of young people.

In general, the makhalla, firstly, as a place of a healthy social environment, regulates human behavior, relationships on the basis of justice and moral criteria. Today, the role and influence of the neighborhood when thinking about improving our spiritual life. It is certainly appropriate to dwell on. From time immemorial, our neighborhoods have been a place of true national values. The main goal of the reforms in this system is to turn the neighborhood into a place where people are aware of the situation day and night. "In the process of implementing the important principle "From a strong state to a strong civil society", first of all, we must rely on the support, strength, capabilities and assistance of such so-called social institutions. Becoming a local colleague,

supporter, "balance of justice" further strengthens people's confidence in the state.

As a result, the work on strengthening peace and harmony in our society will rise to a new level, actively participate in improving the effectiveness of the social system based on the cooperation of school, family and community, which will be justified in life. Today, the role of our makhallas is changing. There is a growing sense of community, trust and commitment. Uzbek communities have always been friendly and cohesive. The influence of the community is very high in our society today. This is because from ancient times, ancient customs and traditions originated in the neighborhood, lived and survived in this environment, and developed under the influence of this environment. Maybe that's why this place is a big family that preserves such ceremonies and passes them on to the younger generation. In this regard, it is not for nothing that our people say, "The family is both a father and a mother for us." It is an expression of vital truth. That's why the Makhalla cares about the peace, tranquility and harmony of our families.

The most important social task of the family is the upbringing of the younger generation. In modern society, the family is seen as the institution of the first socialization of the child. Parents have a socio-cultural character and are distinguished by a system of norms and rules established by culture and society, which regulate the distribution of parenting and parenting responsibilities among parents: the content of roles, models of role behaviors designation Parents are responsible to society at each stage of ontogeny in creating a system of conditions that are appropriate to the child's age characteristics and create optimal opportunities for his or her personal and mental development. In the history of parenting, the growing importance of the institution of the family is becoming more and more evident.

In the age of information globalization, the role of parents in building a vital state, explaining to young people their responsibility and responsibility in

building a sweet state, the importance of their role in the upbringing of children, as well as instilling in the child the national spirit and national values. Education is one of the topical issues of the day. In this regard, the creation of a healthy moral environment in the family and society - the process of education requires great responsibility and attention on the part of parents. A healthy moral and spiritual process is a comprehensive example for a child, a mental and psychological upbringing, an example set by our parents in the upbringing of a child, even from simple words to behavior. and, for example, the study of foreign languages, without forgetting our national traditions, involves the upbringing of children outside the environment without quarrels and disputes, without lawlessness, without immorality.

Let's think about the possible effects of teaching a child a foreign language, we all know that a child learns what he sees and knows in the family, does it, and therefore in vain "does what he sees in the bird's nest" There is no quotation. The process of learning a foreign language first enters the child's brain through his interest in a new nation and country, the more he learns about dress and appearance, lifestyle, the habits of the people learning the language, the style of outlook, you will be able to observe the effects such as walking posture, behavior. As an innovative proposal in teaching foreign languages in our makhallas and families, first of all, from the moment our young child realizes himself, from the moment his family recognizes his parents, we learn our nationality, our national values, from our clothes to our hospitable traditions. I would have suggested that we teach at the same time, we should not give tutors and teachers to bring ordinary children to the level of knowledge of the language faster, but teach our children as games, just as the hospitality of our people is shown in the simple "aunt" game, starting from our kindergartens. then a new environment, I think it makes sense to prepare to teach new languages.

Firstly, it is considered more effective to teach a child words that are language units through clear images and pictures and even action games.

Because when a child sees or does everything, he quickly learns and masters. In families, educational institutions, neighborhoods and enterprises, young people with the ability to think independently and make decisions are the socially necessary for the spiritual development of young people. a pedagogically healthy and stable environment is created. One of the initiatives taken by the President was the decision to "teach foreign languages to children of kindergarten age, and English in schools from the 1st grade on the basis of the integration of disciplines." foreign language skills and the opportunity to acquire knowledge under a healthy environment to the outside world.

While it is desirable to bring up our children on the basis of science and education, in turn, upbringing is closely linked with spirituality. After all, young people are the future owners. Spiritual education plays an important role in the education of our youth. Most importantly, let's pay attention to the upbringing of our children, this is the criterion for our children to grow up spiritually healthy, respectful of their ancestors, our history, our Motherland, our mother tongue, our national values. is the basis of its growth.

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